

Exploring skills in the use of information and communication technologies for teaching (ICTE) among future French language teachers in the secondary cycle.

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ABSTRACT

The use of information and communication technologies for teaching/learning purposes plays a key role in innovating and diversifying teaching methods. It is also important to make the learner active and motivated. Indeed, the effectiveness of the pedagogical integration of information and communication technologies depends on the teacher's mastery of these tools.

The aim of our research is to examine and explore the competences in the use of information and communication technologies for teaching (ICT) among future secondary school teachers of French, who undergo their initial training at the Rabat teacher training centre.

Our perspective is to verify whether the future teachers targeted have the skills required to integrate information and communication technologies into their lessons. course. To answer our problem, we opted for the hypothetical-deductive approach and the quantitative approach. We relied on the questionnaire as a data collection tool. In its design, we specified

a section containing questions on ICT literacy. We formulated these questions according to We formulated these questions according to the objectives of using ICT in the teaching/learning process, We formulated these questions in relation to the objectives of using ICT in the teaching/learning process, as outlined in the ICTE module in the initial teacher training programme. teachers.

Analysis of the data shows that, firstly, the future teachers have at least one technological tool linked to the Internet and are used to these uses; they use them to search for or store information, exchange with colleagues or trainers and study. Secondly, all the respondents stated that they had received ICTE training during their initial training at the regional centre for education and training in Rabat. Thirdly, most future teachers

thirdly, most future teachers justify their mastery of digital educational resources and their ability to thirdly, most future teachers justify their mastery of digital educational resources and their ability to integrate them into the classroom, which confirms our research hypothesis. And fourthly, we found that just fourthly, we found that just the

minority of future teachers who had integrated ICTE into their practicum period while the rest did not use these tools because of the absence of computer equipment in the schools.

Keyword: *ICT, professional skills, future teachers, initial training, FLE.*

1. Introduction

The teacher, through the use of these digital tools, has several opportunities to innovate in the choice of teaching methods; for example, adopting the flipped classroom, which aims to make learners work before the lesson and to devote the time of the session to deepening certain notions, answering learners' questions, discussions, exercises, practical work and remedying gaps. Thanks to ICT, this type of practice becomes easier because teachers make documents and educational videos available to learners in a flexible digital workspace that can be consulted at any time. As a result, learners often take better ownership of the course content presented through ICT than when it is delivered in a traditional way.

In this context, several pedagogical strategies are available to solve the problem of learner motivation. Among these, we mention the integration of a set of means that are of particular interest in terms of the possibilities they offer in terms of activities and influences on the teaching and learning of pupils: information and communication technologies for education (ICTE). Indeed, pupils seem to be very interested in this wave of technology, which they integrate into all their daily activities through the use of smartphones (videos, games, surfing the Internet, etc.). It would therefore be wise to direct these uses to achieve educational goals.

It is therefore becoming imperative for teachers to acquire the necessary skills to use ICT effectively in their teaching. It is also necessary for the various institutions responsible for teacher training to ensure that teachers have developed valid skills in this field, because even if we note that one of the strategies of the national education system consists of equipping all schools with technological means and multimedia supports, all this effort will be ineffective if we are confronted with a lack of ICT skills among teachers.

2. PROBLEMATIC AND METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

Each study is born out of a research problem to be solved. Based on the findings, remarks, experiences and **consultations of various studies and literature reviews, the researcher determines a research problem and the researcher determines a research problem and outlines a working methodology to be followed.**

In this chapter we present the problem, the hypothesis and the objective of our research. We also specify the research methodology, including the choice of epistemological posture, the mode of reasoning, the research method, the data collection and data collection and processing tool.

2.1 The research problem

Information and communication technologies for education (ICTE) include all digital resources that allow access to, dissemination of or production of information for educational purposes. They offer an infinite range of knowledge, methods and tools designed to learn or teach. These tools allow pedagogical innovation, ensure the motivation of learners, make the learner active and diversify teaching/learning methods. The status of the French language in Morocco occupies a special place; it is the first compulsory modern language in the school context and also the language of instruction in many higher education courses (Laroui, 2011, p 74). Aware of the importance of this language, several research studies have been carried out to improve its mastery.

This researcher carried out an experiment with two classes; one with ICTE and the other without ICTE and generalized the experiment to 20 French teachers spread over a large number of schools (public and private colleges). The use of ICTE took place in a multimedia classroom, and the teacher used the free software Hot Potatoes which gave good results since the learners were attentive, curious and motivated, which is not the case for the learners in the class without ICTE. From this, we deduce that educational technologies occupy a crucial place in the teaching/learning of FLE. Different bodies such as the OECD or UNESCO mention the importance of using ICT effectively to support students' teaching and learning (Ananiadou and Claro, 2009; Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2015; UNESCO, 2011). Roland and Vanmeerhaeghe (2016) believe that

the integration and use of technology for pedagogical purposes is, with a few exceptions, not very present in the training of future teachers in primary and secondary schools. Another Moroccan study, which aimed to identify the place of ICTE in teaching practice, showed from the quantitative research conducted that except for half of the teachers surveyed who had received training in ICTE. (Abdelfettah Nacer Idrissi, *Les TICE au Maroc: entre usage et gestion, cas de l'enseignement du français dans le cycle collégial à Agadir*, 2018). From the above, we deduce that the effective use of ICTE in a classroom depends on the techno-pedagogical skills of teachers. In this sense, the training of teachers is considered an essential lever to achieve these skills.

In the light of the above, we can formulate our research problematic around the examination of the competences of the use of information and communication technologies among future French language teachers in order to understand the extent to which they are able to integrate ICT into their courses.

We take as our object of study the future teachers of French in the secondary cycle who are undergoing their initial training at the Regional Center for Education and Training in Rabat.

2.2 Research question:

This issue leads to the following central question: What image do future secondary school French teachers in pre-service training at the regional center for education and training reflect of their skills in information and communication technology for teaching? In other words, do the future secondary school French teachers who are doing their initial training at the regional center for education and training have the skills required to integrate information and communication technologies into their courses?

2.3 Research hypothesis:

In order to answer the research question, we posed earlier, we hypothesize the following:

Hypothesis: Future secondary school teachers of French who receive their initial training at the regional center for education and training in Rabat, could have the necessary skills in the use of information and communication technologies that would allow them to integrate these technologies in their daily teaching.

2.4 Purpose of the research

The purpose of this exploratory study is to examine and explore the use of information and communication technologies for teaching among future secondary school teachers of the French language in initial training at the regional center for education and training of Rabat and this to ensure their ability to integrate the ICTE in the process of teaching French

3. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

3.1 Data processing tools

To process the data, we used SPSS software and Google Forms software. The SPSS software is a particularly suitable tool for implementing statistical data analysis techniques. It is used for a wide range of statistical analyses. The Google Forms software allows to make statistical graphs for each question in an automatic way and to visualize the answers in an Excel file.

The data analysis phase is essential and indispensable in every research project.

After the stage of data collection via the questionnaire, we use the two software of SPSS and Google Forms to analyze and interpret the results.

We present the data collected after the statistical analysis via graphs and tables. Then, we interpret the data presented to verify our research hypothesis and answer our problem.

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The target population was 146 future teachers.

Trainee teachers responded to the questionnaire; this justifies a response rate of 55.5% as shown in the table below:

Future teachers	
Total number of future teachers of the French language in secondary school.	146
Number of those who responded to the questionnaire	81
Percentage of total workforce (Response rate)	55.5 %

- **Ability to use some educational technology resources**

We find that 79.4% of respondents are able to digitize lessons via podcasts using Audacity software. Also, more than a third of the respondents (39.7%) are able to create educational videos using Camtasia Studio software. In addition, the future teachers are able to integrate ICT in evaluation sessions or remediation activities via Quizlet, Hot Potatoes and Kahoot with a percentage of 14.30%, and 12.7% successively. Four respondents added the three software Powtoon, Edpuzzle and Adobe Premier Pro for creating and editing videos and the Microsoft Teams tool for giving classes in video conferencing mode.

- **Ability to teach at a distance**

The graph above shows that almost all of the respondents (97.50%) are competent to teach at a distance, while two are competent to teach at a distance, while two respondents state the opposite.

3.2 Discussion of the results

The present research allowed us to explore the competences in the use of ICT among future secondary school teachers of French, who are undergoing their initial training at the regional center for education and training in Rabat. In general, the results indicate that that the respondents recognize that they have a certain level of competence.

The hypothesis of our research is to explore whether future secondary school teachers of French, who undergo their initial training at the Center for Education and Training in Rabat, have the necessary skills to integrate ICT into their teaching practices.

The first finding of the survey is that the daily life of future teachers is increasingly marked by ICT, since almost all of them have at least one technological tool (smartphone, tablet, fixed computer, laptop) linked to the Internet.

In general, the results of the survey are encouraging in several respects. Indeed, Future teachers have the necessary equipment to familiarize themselves with ICT and to master the with ICT and mastery of basic tools. The data collected indicate that future teachers regularly use teachers regularly use ICT to communicate, search, store and exchange information. exchange information.

Similarly, the majority of the future teachers, more than 70%, affirmed their ability to

- Mastery of the concept of the digital educational resource.
- Presentation of the course via ICT.
- Selection of a digital resource appropriate to the course objective.
- Plan a session that integrates ICT.
- Management of a session that integrates ICT.
- Evaluation or remediation of learner deficiencies using ICT.

This confirms our research hypothesis and shows us that the objectives set out for the ICTE module in the initial training program for future teachers at the at the regional center for education and training have been achieved.

The descriptive analysis of the results also shows that more than three quarters of the future teachers did not use ICT to teach during their internship. They justified this by the unavailability of the digital environment (video projector, computer.) and only 15% of the respondents mentioned their incompetence in the use of technological tools.

However, 18.5% of the future teachers used ICTE during their internship to promote learner motivation, pedagogical innovation and diversify teaching/learning methods. The availability of computer equipment encouraged them to integrate these tools into their practices during the practicum; this confirms that some schools are better equipped than others.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of the present research was to explore the competences in the use of information and communication technologies for teaching (ICTE) among future teachers of the French language in the secondary cycle who are undergoing their initial training at the Center for Education and Training in Rabat.

This research aimed to probe the reality of mastery of educational technologies by future teachers because even if we note that one of the strategies of the national education consists in equipping all schools with technological means.

schools with technological means and multimedia supports, all this effort will be without effectiveness if we effort will be ineffective if we are confronted with a lack of ICT skills among teachers. skills among teachers.

The analysis of the quantitative data shows that all of the future teachers targeted are familiar with familiar with technology since all of them possess at least one technological tool related to the technological, tools related to the Internet and they use these tools regularly to communicate research, exchange, store information and study.

Also, the majority of the future teachers affirmed their mastery of the different aspects of the integration of ICT: the choice of a digital resource appropriate to the course objective, the planning of a session , session planning, management, course presentation, evaluation, and remediation activities; This confirms that future secondary school teachers of French, who receive their initial training at the their initial training at the Center for Education and Training in Rabat, reflect a positive image of their skills in information and communication technologies for teaching.

In addition, only a minority of the pre-service teachers were able to integrate ICT to teach in the practicum; they presented the course via Power Point and used educational videos, audio tracks and gave exercises digitized by quiz creation software. Those who were not able to use ICT during the course justify this fact by the absence of computer equipment in the institution. Therefore, we deduce that some schools are better equipped than others; this reveals other obstacles to the integration of ICT by teachers such as the lack of equipment in the schools.

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